

Solid State Studies of Sodium and Potassium Salts of Mixed Heteropoly Molybdotungstoselenite and Molybdotungstotellurite

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The possibilities of using a solid phase reaction between $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 - \text{H}_2\text{SeO}_3 - \text{H}_2\text{MoO}_4$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 - \text{H}_2\text{TeO}_3 - \text{H}_2\text{MoO}_4$ have been studied to establish the methods of synthesis of mixed heteropoly complexes $\text{Na}_9[\text{WSeMo}_8\text{O}_{32}]18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Na}_9[\text{WTeMo}_8\text{O}_{32}]20\text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively. Their potassium salts have also been prepared. Preliminary X-ray diffraction studies showed the molecular weights of the compounds to be 1980 and 2054 with space groupings $D_{2h}^2 - P_{nnn}$ and $I4_1/a$ respectively. The molecular weights of the potassium salts of the compounds as shown by X-ray studies are 2002 and 2262 respectively. The thermal decomposition analysis of the compounds have also been carried out.

THE W-Se-Mo-O and W-Te-Mo-O systems are of much interest due to their application in the oxidation of olefines to unsaturated carboxylic acids¹. So far, however, there has been no systematic investigations of solid state studies of these systems. The properties of cobalt salts of molybdo-selenates and molybdotellurates, by a solid state reaction² have been recently reported³ but they are of very little interest with the present communication. In these systems the position of selenium and tellurium is of much importance because they are active in the oxidation of propylene to acrylic acid⁴. Solution phase studies of W-Te-V system have though been carried out by Nikitina *et.al*⁵ and Derkach *et.al*⁶, no evidences of studies of W-Se-Mo and W-Te-Mo systems are found in chemical literature either in solid or in solution phase.

Experimental

Synthesis of Sodium-9-Heteropoly Molybdotungstoselenite $\text{Na}_9[\text{WSeMo}_8\text{O}_{32}]18\text{H}_2\text{O}$. (I) :

1.29 gm of selenious acid (H_2SeO_3), 10.15 gm of molybdic acid ($\text{H}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) and 3.3 gm of sodium tungstate ($\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), all of B.D.H. make, were taken in a platinum crucible, mixed thoroughly and heated for 8 hrs at 850° in a muffle furnace. The fused mass was digested with 50 ml of water (pH 3.2), evaporated to half of its original volume and left for a few days. Long needle-shaped white transparent crystals, slowly separated out and were collected after 6 days. The compound was recrystallized from hot water mixed with a few drops of alcohol.

Synthesis of Sodium-9-Heteropoly Molybdotungstotellurite $\text{Na}_9[\text{WTeMo}_8\text{O}_{32}]20\text{H}_2\text{O}$. (II) :

For the synthesis of this complex, 1.78 gm of tellurous acid (H_2TeO_3), 10.15 gm of $\text{H}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 3.3 gm of $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were taken in a platinum crucible and mixed thoroughly. The charge was heated for 8 hrs at a controlled temperature of 950 in a muffle furnace. The fused mass was digested with 50 ml of water (pH 2.4). The pH of the aqueous solution was raised to 4.5 by adding 25 ml of a warm solution of 5% aqueous sodium tungstate. The solution was reduced to two-third of its original volume by heating it on a water bath and left for crystallization. Small white shining crystals were collected after an interval of 4 days. The compound was recrystallized thrice from hot water. To get a single isolated crystal of the compound for X-ray studies, here, the pH was raised a little higher (4.5) because white curdy compound would have found to be separated from the aqueous solution (pH 2.4) as such.

The potassium salt of compound (I) was prepared by adding 100 ml of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ solution (0.51 gm of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ dissolved in 100 ml of water) in small portions to an aqueous boiling solution of compound I (2 gm of compound I dissolved in 100 ml of water). Similarly the potassium salt of compound (II) was prepared by adding 100 ml of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ solution (0.47 gm of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ dissolved in 100 ml of water) in small portions to an aqueous boiling solution of compound II (2.09 gm of compound II, dissolved in 100 ml of water). Pale yellow and cream coloured crystals were separated on cooling from compounds (I) and (II) respectively.

Methods of Analysis :

For analysis, the complexes were completely broken by boiling with hot water along with a few pellets of NaOH and neutralizing by dil. H_2SO_4 .

The total content of molybdenum and tungsten in the compounds were determined by using two methods :

Molybdenum was determined : (i) Colorimetrically, using ammonium thiocyanate⁷ and measuring absorption at $520 m\mu$ and (ii) Gravimetrically in the form of lead molybdate⁸.

Tungsten content was determined : (i) Colorimetrically, using hydroquinone⁷ and measuring the absorption at $570 m\mu$ and (ii) Gravimetrically, using α -benzoin-oxime⁸.

The interference of Mo(VI) during the estimation of W(VI) was removed by precipitating them simultaneously by α -benzoinoxime. The precipitate was heated to 525° , cooled and dissolved in 1 : 3 ammonia solution whereby tungsten passed into solution leaving behind molybdenum in the precipitate. From the filtrate, tungsten was estimated as WO_3 by cinchonine hydrochloride method⁸.

Selenium content was determined : (i) Colorimetrically using potassium iodide⁷ and (ii) Gravimetrically, using hydrochloric acid solution⁸ for the separation of elementary selenium.

Tellurium content was determined : (i) Colorimetrically, using potassium iodide⁷ and (ii) Gravimetrically using hydrochloric acid solution⁸ for the separation of elementary tellurium.

Sodium and potassium contents were found out by flame photometer.

Hydrogen was estimated by element estimation technique.

From the analytical data the compounds were formulated : (Found Mo, 38.28 ; W, 9.11 ; Se, 3.92 ; Na, 6.83 ; H, 1.83 ; calc. for $Na_6[WSeMo_8O_{32}] 18H_2O$: Mo, 38.30 ; W, 9.18 ; Se, 3.99 ; Na, 6.88 ; H, 1.84%).

(Found Mo, 36.70 ; W, 8.78 ; Te, 6.11 ; Na, 6.59 ; H, 1.90 ; calc. for $Na_6[WTeMo_8O_{32}] 20H_2O$: Mo, 36.75 ; W, 8.80 ; Te, 6.12 ; Na, 6.60 ; H, 1.91%).

(Found Mo, 37.80 ; W, 9.0 ; Se, 3.42 ; K, 11.00 ; H, 1.36 ; calc. for $K_6[WSeMo_8O_{32}] 14H_2O$: Mo, 37.85 ; W, 9.07 ; Se, 3.88 ; K, 11.53 ; H, 1.38%).

(Found Mo, 33.89 ; W, 7.99 ; Te, 5.52 ; K, 10.20 ; H, 2.25 ; calc. for $K_6[WTeMo_8O_{32}] 26H_2O$: Mo, 33.47 ; W, 8.02 ; Te, 5.58 ; K, 10.20 ; H, 2.27%).

The final representation of the formulae of the compounds were according to the view suggested by Pauling *et al*⁹. for the parent heteropoly anion $[X^nMo_9O_{32}]^{-(10-n)}$.

X-ray Diffraction Studies of the Compounds :

X-ray crystal diffraction analyses of compound (I) and (II) showed that they are isostructural. Photographs of a single crystal of sodium-9-molybdo-tungstoselenite reveal for $Na_6[SeMo_8WO_{32}] 18H_2O$ a orthorhombic cell, $a = 12.56$, $b = 15.15$, $c = 9.85 \text{ \AA}$ and $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$, volume per unit cell, $V = 1876 \text{ \AA}^3$. The space group is $D_{2h}^2 - P_{nnn}$. The number of unit cell contained $Z = 2$. measured density, $D_m = 3.5 \text{ gcc}^{-1}$. The molecular weight, $M_{obs.}$ of the compound, calculated from the relation $D_m = \frac{1.66 M.Z}{V}$ comes to 1980 as compared with the calculated value 2004. The results of the X-ray crystal diffraction studies for the other compounds are given below :

(II) $K_6[SeMo_8WO_{32}] 14H_2O$: $a = 14.21$, $b = 9.24$, $c = 14.50 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$, $V = 1903.76 \text{ \AA}^3$, Orthorhombic system, $Z = 2$, $D_m = 3.4 \text{ gcc}^{-1}$, $M_{obs.} = 2002$ against $M \text{ calc} = 2029$.

(III) $Na_6[TeMo_8WO_{32}] 20H_2O$: $a = 17.23$, $b = 10.56$, $c = 12.12 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$, $V = 2205.21 \text{ \AA}^3$, $Z = 2$, space group $I 4 1/a$, $D_m = 3.0 \text{ gcc}^{-1}$, $M_{obs.} = 2054$ against $M \text{ calc.} = 2089$.

(IV) $K_6[TeMo_8WO_{32}] 26H_2O$: $a = 16.79$, $b = 10.21$, $c = 15.30 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$, Orthorhombic system, $V = 2622.74 \text{ \AA}^3$, $Z = 2$, $D_m = 2.7 \text{ gcc}^{-1}$, $M_{obs.} = 2262$ against $M \text{ calc} = 2293$.

Thermal Behaviour of the Compounds :

The heteropoly acids and their salts can be regarded as condensation inorganic polymers¹⁰. To know stepwise loss of water molecules and the final decomposition temperature of the compound, their thermal degradation studies¹⁰ have been made at different temperatures on the basis of the investigations made by West and Audrith¹¹ on a few heteropoly compounds. Known amounts of the samples were taken in a platinum crucible, heated in a controlled high temperature furnace and the samples were weighed and analysed successively at different temperatures. The systematic loss of water molecules and the surrounding optimum temperature at which the compounds were broken as a whole into

its lower oxides are tabulated below :

Compounds	Loss of water molecules						*Decomposition Temp. °C
	60°	120°	200°	300°	400°	500°	
(1) $\text{Na}_6[\text{WSeMo}_8\text{O}_{32}]\cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$	—	2 mol	1 mol	4 mol	4 mol	—	750 ± 10
(2) $\text{Na}_6[\text{WTeMo}_8\text{O}_{32}]\cdot 20\text{H}_2\text{O}$	—	3 mol	2 mol	5 mol	2 mol	—	820 ± 10
(3) $\text{K}_6[\text{WSeMo}_8\text{O}_{32}]\cdot 14\text{H}_2\text{O}$	—	3 mol	1 mol	4 mol	—	—	725 ± 10
(4) $\text{K}_6[\text{WTeMo}_8\text{O}_{32}]\cdot 26\text{H}_2\text{O}$	—	2 mol	1 mol	7 mol	5 mol	2 mol	780 ± 10

* Decomposition of the compounds into their lower oxides.

From the above table it is clear that in all the heteropoly salts prepared, their water of crystallization eliminated out nearly in 400-500° range. Rest 6 to 8 water molecules remained intact in the crystal lattice as the water of constitution. The number of water of constitution in the compounds agreed closely with the views of Scroggie and Clark^{1,2} with comparable compounds. To remove water of constitution, the compounds were heated to a still higher temperature. Nearly at 750 to $820 \pm 10^\circ$ the compounds were broken as a whole into the basic units of lower oxides of the constituent metals.

Discussion

The representative mixed heteropoly compounds prepared here are basically 1 : 9 heteropoly molybdates of the present heteroanion $[\text{X}^n\text{Mo}_9\text{O}_{32}]^{-(10-n)}$ where one MoO_6 octahedra has been replaced by one WO_6 octahedron. The structures of these heteropoly compounds will be similar to that of Pauling's⁹ heteroanion $[\text{X}^n\text{Mo}_9\text{O}_{32}]^{-(10-n)}$ with a slight distortion due to the replacement of one of MoO_6 octahedra by one WO_6 octahedron. Comparing the thermal stabilities of the compounds with those of silicomolybdates^{1,2} and phosphomolybdates^{1,3} it may be concluded that greater the positive charge on the central ion $[\text{Mo}_9\text{O}_{32}]^{-10}$, more effective is the binding in the resulting heteropoly anion, stabilizing the latter against thermal vibrations and resultant decomposition.

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